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Effect of School Related Variables on Students' Happiness: An Analytical Study

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Abstract

School is most important place where students spent most of their active and creative times. The school includes both physical environment and social atmosphere which is purposefully plan, designed and prepare for all round/ holistic development of each learner according to their need and capability. Many researches and studies showed about the importance of school environments in the development of learners. The school infrastructure and facilities play an important role in shaping the students personality. Conducive infrastructure promotes a safe, comfortable & convenient environment for students' learning. The important factors affecting happiness are School infrastructures and facilities, activities, extra-curricular activities, relationships (human factor), personal and academic achievements, carefulness and self-confidence and school habitat. The school infrastructure and facilities affect students holistically. Student spent half of their active time/ life in school and classrooms. Thus, school infrastructure and facilities play an important role in shaping the students personality. This paper is based upon descriptive research study in which the students' happiness measured about some selected school variables on Student Happiness scale. The data was analyzed and made a conclusion.

Keywords : Happiness, School Infrastructure, School Event Celebration, Govt. Scheme, Peer relationship, Teachers' Support, School Environment and Locations.

Introduction

A welcoming school environment helps students to learn effectively and develop their skills. A happy school environment can help student learn creativity, and makes healthy relationships. School happiness is an important enabler for ensuring that all learners complete free, equitable and quality primary and secondary education leading to relevant and effective learning outcomes by 2030 (Sustainable Development Goal Target- 4.1). UNESCO supports policy-makers to re-imagine education systems from the happiness point of views, considering the people, processes, places, and principles that make going to school a happy and creative experience for all. In the future, UNESCO aims to engage more nations to develop a national happy schools framework. It will help policy-makers and administrators to develop, implement, and monitor policies and programmes to enhance happiness in schools to improve learning.

The important factors affecting happiness are School infrastructures and facilities, activities, extra- curricular activities, relationships (human factor), personal and academic achievements, carefulness and self-confidence and school habitat. The school infrastructure and facilities affect students holistically. Student spent half of their active time/ life in school and classrooms. Thus, school infrastructure and facilities play an important role in shaping the students personality. The student percept about the outer world is mostly based upon their school experiences. An academic study by UK researchers revealed that a school building- 'a *home away from home*' for students contribute to 16% of a child's academic progress. Design elements of school infrastructure integrate three crucial factors that encourage a child's learning.

- **Conduciveness** for comfort and inspiration
- **Stimulation** through colour, complexity & resources
- **Personalization** to encourage engagement, individual participation & progress

Conducive infrastructure promotes a safe, comfortable & convenient environment for students' learning. The school washrooms, classrooms, corridors and ramps have been designed considering different age groups and abilities. The girl students are more than half in schools for their special need a

dress and sanitary pad changing room make them more confident, safe and happy. These facilities help in their academic development by increasing their presence in the school. Proper ventilation, lightening, furnished with furniture for seating, clean and decorated classrooms make children comfortable and happy at school. Clean and safe drinking water is basic physiological need of each student. Students have interest and are happy by play, so playground is important infrastructure of the school for their happiness and holistic development. The library equipped with proper reading facility and course books, magazine, newsletters etc is necessary to develop reading habits, skills like use of leisure time, language, creative thinking and experiences of past human endeavors. Learning corner facility in classroom provides extra opportunity of learning, reading, interacting with facts, past experiences and present challenges to teachers and peers. The decoration of classroom walls with different knowledgeable pictures, scenery makes school environment attractive, welcoming and appealing, this lead to student happiness and better development. Building as Learning Aid (BaLA) is an innovative concept that aims to improve education by creating a child-friendly, fun, and learning-based physical environment in school infrastructure. The concept assumes that the school's architecture can be a resource for the teaching-learning processes. Attractive school and well-furnished classroom increases student attentiveness, regular attendance, makes better learning, creates more fun activities and cause holistic skill/ talent development.

In June, 2018 'Operation Kayakalpa' was launched by U.P. government. It is intergovernmental convergence programs. Under this, funds have been specially made available by the Central and State Government for various initiatives like Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA), Gram Panchayat Fund, District Mineral Fund, various funds of urban area, Jal Jeevan Mission, MNREGA etc. The basic infrastructural facilities of Upper Primary Schools in each district of U.P. are being revamped. As a result, 'Operation Kayakalp' has given a new looks to the schools of villages and towns located in remote areas. Significant changes have now taken place in hundreds of schools in the state. These schools have digital class rooms with gates, boundary walls, floor tiles, play parks and libraries, separate toilets for boys and girls, drinking water and hand washings system, well furnished classrooms for children. After getting the facility of furniture, the smiles and happiness on the faces of the children studying here are telling the success story of rejuvenation.

Nothing is better than instilling joy and fun into the lives of our learners; big and small (Katie Neumeier, 2022). Students participate in various school events with enthusiasm and joy, which increases their positive emotions and ultimately to happiness. Through various school events, along with socialization, team sprite, collaborative work culture, interpersonal contact skill and various types of psychomotor skills are learned naturally and actively. Extra and co-curricular activities are necessary for holistic development of the student's personality and skills. Annual function, Game and sports, collective birthday celebration, TLM fair, Science exhibition and national festival event give opportunity for all round personality development with joyful activities. The involvement of community members, parents provides joy and confidence. Proper and quality full MDM serving makes children energize and happy. All most all children (97.83%) were satisfied with the MDM scheme and wanted to continue (97.33%) the scheme.

Under the Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA), each upper primary school is buying sports equipment like football, handball, volleyball net, softball etc. UP Free School Uniform Scheme 2023 is a new initiative of the state govt. where govt. has transferred money to beneficiaries to enable them to purchase a uniform, sweater, socks, school bags, shoes. The amount of Rs. 1200 under UP Free School Bag / Uniform / Sweaters / Shoes scheme is send to the accounts of the parents of class 1st to 8th students. Money is send to the parents of beneficiary students through Direct Benefit Transfer (DBT) mode i.e., directly into their bank accounts. The School Health Programme (SHP) under Ayushman Bharat launched is a joint collaborative program of the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare and the Ministry of Human Resource Development. Under school health Check-up programs student learns hygiene practices like hand washing, toilet etiquette, and menstrual health. They can also spread awareness about physical health, nutrition, prevention of illnesses, usage of safe drinking water, and meditation and other techniques for mental well-being.

Peer relationships can help students to learn social-emotional skills like sympathy, empathy, cooperation, and problem-solving abilities. Positive peer-relationships give emotional well-being. Peer relationships can also have negative effects, such as beating, bullying, exclusion, and indiscipline. There

is evidence that peer relationship and support are an important part of the school context for children and early adolescents, significantly enhancing to their happiness, school liking, academic achievement, and wellness (Wentzel et al., 2004; Boulton et al., 2011; Oberle and Schonert-Reichl, 2013; Sebanc et al., 2016). There are strong evidences comes from researches that cooperative learning has positive effect on academic achievement and higher order thinking skills (Davidson & major, 2014). The developmental theories of Vygotsky (1986) and Piaget (1951) suggest that when student working together, socio-cognitive-interaction lead to deeper reasoning.

Use of Teaching- learning material (TLM) makes learning easy, interesting and enjoyable. It helps in conceptualize with clarity, learning faster and recall for long time, motivate and encourage the student, thus provides happiness to them. When students find the opportunity to express him-self at a big occasion, assembly, stage etc. becomes confident, courage, aware and happy. Student feel more familiarize, confident, motivated and happy when teacher talk about themselves. Student's getting a deeper belongingness in classroom learning and in other academic activities by teacher rapport. Teacher take information from student's about their contexts, weakness and strength, threats and challenges, it helps in formative assessment and plan about remedial teaching, personalized or individualized teaching-learning and in the changing pedagogy. The counseling/ guidance for better understanding and learning of different skills provide happiness to the students. Evaluation and suggestion about students learning difficulties by teacher to student causes more satisfaction among them. Many studies shown that student with more teacher support have high positive emotions, have more enjoyment, interest, hope, happiness etc. and low negative emotions like anxiety, depression, shame, anger, boredom or hopelessness etc. (Ahmed et al., 2010; King et al., 2012; Tian et al., 2013; McMahon et al., 2013; Lazarides and Ittel, 2013). Use of different modes and media, methods, styles makes teaching- learning more joyful. Science teaching with science kit in lab by demonstration collaboratively makes student more aware, happy and well skilled. Story listening and use of story as teaching- learning methodology makes learning more enjoyable and interactive causing deeper reasoning and imagination. In classroom teaching use of familiar and examples of local contexts make learning more grasping and fun activity. The experiences and previous understanding of student is more important and foundation for new learning. Experiential learning envisage with practical knowledge and seeing/ empirical phenomenon makes clear concept and retain for long times. Use of student's mother tongue and dialect (speak or call) is most important for the purpose of holistic personality development and understandings of concepts and lastly the highest joy is the joy of understanding. The role of teacher supports and affectionate behaviour is more important for student's happiness. Many studies shown the teacher student relationships lead to student happiness (Chu, Saucier, & Hafner, 2010; Suldo et al., 2009; Suldo, Shaffer, & Riley, 2008). The helping act of teacher establish supportive and positive relationships with students, have indirect effect on student happiness, that leads to intrinsic motivation to learn and meaningful engagement and academic achievements (Froiland & Worrell, 2018; Froiland, Davidson, & Worrell, 2016; Levesque et al., 2004).

Location of school can affect student happiness in a number of way, students who attend a nearby school spend less time commuting and have more time for other activities. A positive school climate like greening, pollution free and free from noises can increase student happiness. Peaceful and natural habitat of a school is important for student happiness. Ease of accessibility, availability of convenient transportation and venue in less-crowded/ uncongested area is also an important reason behind student happiness.

The factors influencing student's happiness are learning skills, attitude and knowledge can lead to the satisfaction towards the happiness of learning among the students (Somtop, K., 2014). Socialization is one way of achieving happiness; the more social activities, the happier the individuals in school. The academic factors are important in creating happiness. There is a positive and direct relationship between academic achievements and happiness. Physical factors, participative and supportive leadership style were important in creating happiness in school. There is a strong and positive relationship between happiness and self-esteem (Fatemeh Talebzadeh, 2011). Curriculum will not only affect student's attitudes towards school and learning environment, but will also affect student's happiness. Happiness will make positive attitudes among students and may lead to higher academic achievements and eventually more active and regular citizens (Tenney, Jodiann, K., 2011). An important criterion for happy school is positive teacher's attitudes and attributes such as kindness, enthusiasm, fairness and the role in serving as inspiring, creative and happy role models for learners (Lee & Lee,

2014). The affectionate behavior of teacher towards the students, not only give motivation to the students but makes good achievements and happiness as shown in the movie Taare Zameen Par (2008). Happy students learn more actively, more creative and spend more quality time for their school related activities thus learn better when they are happier (Adler, A., 2016). The children who were asked to think happy thoughts before starting the task did learn better than the others, and completed it faster and with few errors. All human activities are ultimately for obtaining happiness. Happiness lies in the outer environment or within us. According to A. Nagraj (1999), 'a state of no-conflict, synergy, or a state of being in acceptance is Happiness'. The inner state of happiness promotes factors that allow individuals to flourish with high acceptance and greater extent. Happy people also have meaningful relationships with others and the strong social skills and high emotional intelligence needed to form them (Csikszentmihalyi, M., K. R. Rathunde, et al., 1993). When people participate in classes outside work, they improve their mental and physical health and report greater satisfaction with their lives (Eiluned Pearce, 2016). Those who engage in formal education experience greater happiness and life satisfaction overall (Ryan T. Howell, David Chenot, Graham Hill & Collen J. Howell, 2009).

Research Questions

1. What is happiness among middle stage students in school?
2. Whether the happiness among middle stage students is related with school variables like infrastructures of school, school celebrations, implementation of government schemes, peer relationships, teacher support and school locations?

Statement of the Problem

A Study of Happiness among Middle Stage Students with Reference to School Related Variables

Objectives of the Study

1. To study happiness among the middle stage students with reference to the infrastructure.
2. To study happiness among the middle stage students with reference to the school celebrations
3. To study happiness among the middle stage students with reference to the implementation of government schemes
4. To study happiness among the middle stage students with reference to the peer relationship
5. To study happiness among the middle stage students with reference to the teacher support
6. To study happiness among the middle stage students with reference to the school locations

Assumptions of the Study

Students have different causes of emotions and happiness. In this study the different variables/ causes related with school experiences like different infrastructural facilities in school, different occasion and celebrations in school through years, implementation of different beneficial government schemes, peer relationships, teacher supportive behaviour and school location affects the student's happiness of middle stage students and it can be measured.

Delimitations of the study

In the present study of happiness among middle stage students with reference to school related variables are investigated to the student studying in government upper primary schools located in Ballia district, U. P., India.

Research Design

In the present study descriptive survey research design has been adopted.

Population

In the present study the middle stage students studying in class 6th, 7th and 8th standard from Upper Primary Schools of Basic Shiksha Parishad of Ballia district of Uttar Pradesh were taken as population for analytical study.

Sampling Technique-

In the present study multistage stratified random sampling procedure has applied. The 500 students and 50 teachers taught them were selected from Upper primary schools of Basic Shiksha Parishad, U.P. located in urban and rural areas of Ballia district are selected.

Tools Used in the Study

The happiness of middle stage students was measured through Students Happiness Scale which was developed by the researcher. It is a 5-point Likert's rating scale. The Reliability of Happiness Scale (tool) by Cronbach's alpha method was found to be 0.973 and by split-half method was found to be 0.944. The validity of Students Happiness Scale was established by item analysis (t test) and consulting

experts from different disciplines like Sociology, Education, Psychology, measurement, evaluation and research methodologists and experienced school teachers.

Statistical Technique used

Quantitative approach has been adopted for data analysis. Percentages of scores are obtained and used for data analysis.

Data Analysis

Objective 1. To study happiness among the middle stage students with reference to the infrastructure

Table 1. Student’s happiness towards school infrastructure

Dimension	Strongly agree %	Agree %	Undecided %	Disagree %	Strongly disagree %
School infrastructures	32.23	62.75	4.6	0.33	0.01

The above table and fig. clearly show that most of the students (32.23% are strongly agreed and 62.75% are agreed) about 94.98% are agreed with the school infrastructures like furniture, drinking water, light and fan, separate toilets for boys, girls and disabled, playground, boundary wall, learning-corner, library, attractive wall paintings, tiles installation, hand-wash facility, sanitary pad changing room and incinerator makes them happy.

Objective 2. To study happiness among the middle stage students with reference to the school celebrations

Table 2. Student’s happiness towards school events

Dimension	Strongly agree %	Agree %	Undecided %	Disagree %	Strongly disagree %
School events	37.16	60.94	1.58	0.15	0.17

The above table and fig. clearly show that most of the students (37.16% are strongly agreed and 60.94% are agreed) about 98.10% are agreed with the school events like Independence Day, Republic Day, Teacher’s Day, Children’s Day, annual function, sport competition, collectively birthday, TLM fair, science exhibition, PTA meetings, MTA meetings etc. and participation of their parents and other family members makes them happy.

Objective 3. To study happiness among the middle stage students with reference to the implementation of government schemes

Table3. Student’s happiness towards implementation of government schemes

Dimension	Strongly agree %	Agree %	Undecided %	Disagree %	Strongly disagree %
Implementations of govt. schemes	35.825	61.875	1.825	0.475	0.00

Fig.3. Graphical analysis of the student’s happiness towards implementations government schemes.

The above table and fig. clearly show that most of the students (35.825% are strongly agree and 61.875% are agree) about 97.70% are agree with the implementations of government schemes like MDM preparation regular, quality full and according to menu, free distributions of books and work books, money of DBT for uniform, sweater, socks and shoes, playing equipment and kits, health check- up makes them happy.

Objective 4. To study happiness among the middle stage students with reference to the peer relationship

Table 4. Student’s happiness towards peer relationships

Dimension	Strongly agree %	Agree %	Undecided %	Disagree %	Strongly disagree %
Peer relationships	30.57	67.37	1.54	0.314	0.20

The above table and fig. clearly show that most of the students (30.57% are strongly agree and 67.37% are agree) about 97.94% are agree with the peer relationships like cooperative and collaborative learning, exchange of learning materials, participation in games and sports, learning with playing, making of projects, team learning, group competition, role play, support for learning to each other’s makes them happy.

Objective 5. To study happiness among the middle stage students with reference to the teacher support

Table 5. Student's happiness towards teacher support

Dimension	Strongly agree %	Agree %	Undecided %	Disagree %	Strongly disagree %
Teacher support	33.03	64.06	2.44	0.39	0.073

The above table 4.1.7 and fig. 4.1.5 clearly shows that most of the students (33.03% are strongly agree and 64.06% are agree) about 97.09% are agree with the teacher support, behavior and activities like use of TLM in teaching- learning, provide opportunity to express them to students, to rapport and introduce to students, to apply different methods and strategies to make easy and learnable the subject contents, provide individual diagnostic and remedial teaching, provides learning suggestions on homework evaluations, teaching by different activities, use of science kit and demonstration methods in science teaching, storytelling, provides information on class Whats App group, teaching by discussion, debate and story, alternate seating plan, use of local and familiar examples in teaching, use of mother tongue and local dialect in classroom teaching learning and giving importance to the students experiences in teaching and learning makes them happy.

Objective 6. To study happiness among the middle stage students with reference to the school locations

Table 6. Student's happiness towards school locations

Dimension	Strongly agree %	Agree %	Undecided %	Disagree %	Strongly disagree %
School locations	35.84	60.28	2.72	0.84	0.32

The above table clearly shows that most of the students (35.84% are strongly agree and 60.28% are agree) about 96.12% are agree with the school locations and environments like school near to home or residences, school located at peaceful place and out of city crowd, green environment of school, school path and access is easy makes them happy.

Findings of the study

- The students are agreed to the fact that availability of school infrastructure makes them happy.
- The students are agreed to the fact that organization of different school events and their participation in them makes them happy.
- The students are agreed with the fact that when they eat mid-day meal in the school it provides happiness to the students.
- The statistical analysis showed that about 97.94 % students are agreed to the fact that peer relationships contribute to student's happiness in different ways.
- The statistical analysis showed that about 97.09 % students are agreed to the fact that teacher's support/ behavior contributes to student's happiness in different ways.
- The students are agreed to the fact that school locations and school environment contributes to student's happiness in different ways.

Conclusion

Based on the main objective 1and finding 1 of the study following conclusion has been derived: Middle Stage Students of Ballia district have happiness.

Discussion

The reason behind this may be that they are getting adequate facilities to learn and stay in the school. Their schools provide them with good learning and developmental facilities. The school furnished with good infrastructures. The school organizes many events, functions multidisciplinary and co- curricular activities. So, the students by participation in them feel more connected to school. There are many schemes launched by central and state governments launched are properly implemented in the welfare of students in their school. They have intimate and good peer- relationships. They play and participate in different fun, learning activities with their friends. They have healthy communication with friends and their teachers. The teachers are good, well-trained, educated and have deep understanding of teaching and learning. They incorporate innovative teaching- learning practices. The student feels that their teachers love them so they feel secure and confident. The quality and good relationship make them

happy. Most of the schools have easy accessibility and situated in natural and peaceful habitat, such locations and environment provide extra happiness to the students. Although, some school have lack of proper infrastructures, some school not organizing proper way school events, some school not properly implement different government schemes, some school not manage space for peer interactions, , some teachers traditionally and rigidly working in school, some school located in crowded and have uneasy environment, in such school students have less happiness.

Implications of the Study

- Happiness is an important construct as it is related with the well-being of school student. Present research will be important for school administrators and policymakers to facilitate the teaching learning conditions in school to increase student's happiness and performance.
- School experiences are important in student's life and present research is making establish the empirical evidence towards basic need satisfaction, importance of self-expression, peer relationships, teacher's relationships and environments with happiness of middle stage students.
- Present research will make strong ground for educational stake holders to understand the dynamics of middle stage students' happiness in school.
- In present study majority of the students showed happiness. School infrastructures, school events, implementation of government schemes, peer relationships, teacher's support and school locations and environments significantly affect their happiness rather than their habitat. Thus education contributes happiness, teacher should encourage the students to participate and engage in different learning and developmental activities.
- This study helps to understand the importance of happiness in student's learning and all-round development. It aware and suggests to the educational stake holders like policy makers, administrator, managers, principal and teacher to maintain above given provisions in elementary schools.
- The teacher should careful about infrastructural facilities, organizations of school events, implementations of government schemes, peer interactions, students-teachers' interactions and school locations and environments because these variables are directly related to student's happiness.
- The teacher should encourage cooperative, collaborative, participatory teaching methods to facilitate strong peer relationships among middle stage students.
- The present study suggests that teacher-student relationship is an indicator of happiness. So, the teacher should be supportive, democratic, cooperative, affectionate and self-disciplinary behavior encouraged in the classroom. The teacher should try to establish strong teacher-student relationship.
- Present study suggests the teacher should be sympathetically treats to students. The teacher should cooperate and motivate the students for learning, give individual dignity and respect them. Teacher should be sound and objective while dealing students. Teacher should use student's language and dialect in personal and group interactions in classroom and outside.
- The present research makes the empirical ground for maintaining the healthy, pleasant and conducive learning environment in upper primary schools which is important for the development and learning of children.

References & Bibliography

- Adler, A. (2016). Teaching Well Being increases Academic Performance: Evidence from Bhutan, Mexico and Peru. Publicly Accessible Penn. Dissertation.1572.
- Ahmed, W., Minnaert, A., Van der Werf, G.,and Kuyper, H. (2010). Percieved social support and early adolescents' achievement: the meditational role of motivational beliefs and emotions. *J. Youth Adolesc.* 39, 36-46. Doi: 10.1007/s10964-008-9367-7
- Boulton, M. J., Don, J., & Boulton, L. (2011). Predicting children's liking of school from their peer relationships. *Social Psychology of Education*, 14, 489-501.
- Chu, P., Saucier, D., & Hafner, E. (2010). Meta-analysis of the relationships between social support and wellbeing in children and adolescents. *Journal of Social and Clinical Psychology*, 29, 624–645.
- Csikszentmihalyi, M., K. R. Rathunde, et al. (1993). *Talented Teenagers : The Roots of Success and Failure*. Cambridge England ; New York, N.Y., Cambridge University Press. Retrieved from https://greatergood.berkeley.edu/article/item/the_childhood_roots_of_adult_happiness_an_annotated_bibliography at 05. 11. 2023.
- Cuyvers, K., et al. (2011): Well-being at school: Does infrastructure matter? ISSN 2072-7925 Corrigenda to OECD publications may be found on line at:www.oecd.org/publishing/corrigenda. retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/254439615_Well-Being_at_School_Does_Infrastructure_Matter at 20. 11. 2023.

- ET Education.Com. from The Economic Times (2023): UP govt. release money for sports material for school. Retrieved from <https://education.economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/school-education/up-govt-releases-money-for-sports-material-for-all-schools/104454993#:~:text=Under%20the%20Samagra%20Shiksha%20scheme,volleyball%20net%2C%20softball%20among%20others>. At 10. 11. 2023.
- Fatemeh Talebzadeh, (2011): An Evolution of the Factors Influencing Happiness among Female Students of Elementary School in Rehta, International Conference on Social Science and Humanity IPDER, Vol.5 (2011) IASCIT Press, Singapore retrieved from [uper.com/ vol. / no 2/ 98-H10240.pdf](http://uper.com/vol./no2/98-H10240.pdf) at 22.09.2021.
- Froiland, J. M., & Davison, M. L. (2016). The longitudinal influences of peers, parents, motivation, and mathematics course taking on high school math achievement. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 50, 252-259. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2016.07.012>
- Froiland, J. M., Davison, M. L., Worrell, F. C. (2016). Aloha teachers: Teacher autonomy support promotes Native Hawaiian and Pacific Islander students' motivation, school belonging, course- taking and math achievement. *Social Psychology of Education*, 19, 879–894.
- Froiland, J. M. & Worrell, F. C. (2016). Intrinsic motivation, learning goals, engagement, and achievement in a diverse high school. *Psychology in the Schools*, 53, 321–336. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pits.21901>
- India Today Web Desk (2017): This is why a school infrastructure is important for a child's growth. retrieved from <https://www.indiatoday.in/education-today/featurephilia/story/school-infrastructure-importance-981989-2017-06-10> at 09. 11. 2023
- King, R. B., Mc Inerney, D. M., and Watkins, D. A. (2012). How you think about your intelligence determines how you feel in school: the role of theories of intelligence on academic emotions. *Learn. Individ. Differ.* 22, 814-819. doi: 10.1016/j.lindif.2012.04.005
- Lazarides, R., & Ittel, A. (2013). Mathematics interest and achievement: what role do perceived parent and teacher play? A longitudinal analysis. *Int. J. Gender Sci. Tech.* 5, 207- 231. Available online at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/260690091>
- Levesque, C., Zuehlke, A. N., Stanek, L. R., & Ryan, R. M. (2004). Autonomy and competence in German and American university students: A comparative study based on self-determination theory. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 96, 68–84.
- McMohan, D. (2006). *Happiness: A history*. Grove Press.
- Mertoglu, M. (2019): Factors Affecting Happiness of School Children. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, Vol. 8, No. 3; March 2020, ISSN 2324- 805X, E- ISSN 2324- 8068, Published by Redfame Publishing. doi: 1011114/jets.v8i3.4674 URL: <https://doi.org/1011114jets.v8i3.4674> retrieved from <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/287230556.pdf> at 14. 11. 2023.
- Neumeier, K. (2022): 12 Fun School Event Ideas Students (& Teacher) Will Love. *Live School*. Retrieved from <https://www.whyliveschool.com/blog/fun-school-event-ideas> at 09. 11. 2023.
- Operation Kayakalp. (2018): Department of Basic Education, Government of Uttar Pradesh. Retrieved from <https://basiceducation.up.gov.in/en/page/operation-kayakalp> at 09. 11. 2023.
- PVR Pictures presents Aamir productions; produced and directed by Aamir Khan; co-producers Ajay Bijli and Sanjiv K. Bijli. *Taare Zameen Par. Every Child Is Special*. New Delhi: Super Cassettes Industries, 2008.
- Somtop, K. (2014): Factors Affecting Happiness Learning of Students of Faculty of Management Science, Suna Sugandha Rajaghat University, Bangkok, *International Science Index, Economics and Management Engineering*, Vol. 8, No. 6, 2014 wasn't. org/ publication/ 9998565 retrieved at 22. 09. 2021.
- Suldo, S. M., Shaffer, E. J., & Riley, K. N. (2008). A social-cognitive-behavioral model of academic predictors of adolescents' life satisfaction. *School Psychology Quarterly*, 23, 56–70.
- Tenney, Jodiann, K., (2011): Factors Affecting the Happiness of Urban Elementary School: Exploratory study, Pro Quest, LLC, Ed. D. Dissertation, Southern Connecticut State University, ISBN-978-11249-9166-5 retrieved at 22. 09. 2021
- UNESCO. (2023): “Happy School” for better learning. 42nd Session of the General Conference from 7 to 22 November 2023. Retrieved from <https://www.unesco.org/en/education-policies/happy-schools> at 07. 11. 2023.
- Upadhyay, B. & Geeta, K. (2019): Opinion and nutritional status of children consuming mid day meal (MDM) in school in Delhi. Retrieved from <https://www.researchpublish.com/upload/book/Opinion%20and%20nutritional%20status-7927.pdf> at 10.11. 2023.
- Varthana (2022): 5 Reasons Why School Infrastructure is Important for A Child's Growth. retrieved from <https://varthana.com/school/5-reasons-why-school-infrastructure-is-important-for-a-childs-growth/> at 09. 11. 2023.
- Wizarat, K. (2009): Study of Best Practices Adopted in Mid- Day- Meal Scheme in Uttar Pradesh. Retrieved from <https://www.educationforallindia.com/best-practices-mid-day-meal-uttar-pradesh-kausar-waizrat.pdf> at 10. 11. 2023.

